

Framework for holistic assessment of water smartness and progress towards SDGs

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this deliverable is to present the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework developed in work package 5. The report describes the development and presents the version of the framework to be tested in the demonstration cases in the project. In WIDER UPTAKE, the point of departure for measuring water smartness is Water Europe’s definition of a water-smart society, while achieving sustainability implies achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The presented framework builds upon existing sustainability assessment frameworks and has been further developed through input and feedback from stakeholders in WIDER UPTAKE through workshops in the local communities of practise. The suggested content of the framework has been found relevant for the demonstration cases, and a group of SDGs (SDG 6, 9, 11, 12 and 13), are found to be highly relevant for the cases. The content of the framework to be tested in the demonstration cases concludes this report.

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Executive summary

To meet European and global water challenges, a transition to a water-smart society has been foreseen in Water Europe's vision 'The Value of Water' [1,2]. In WIDER UPTAKE, symbiotic circular economy solutions are co-developed by private companies and drinking- and wastewater utilities to achieve wider uptake of water-smart solutions. These solutions should also be sustainable, i.e., contribute to the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In work package 5 (WP5), a framework for assessing water smartness and progress towards the SDGs for symbiotic circular economy solutions is under development. This report presents the development and framework version to be tested in the project's demonstration cases.

The WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework has been co-developed with the stakeholders in the local communities of practice in the project's demonstration cases, building on previous sustainability assessment frameworks for the water sector. Keywords in Water Europe's definition of a water-smart society has been the point of departure for measuring water smartness:

- Value of and in water
- Water management
- Water scarcity
- Water pollution
- Circularity and resource efficiency
- Resilience
- Symbiotic circular economy solutions (the water system in WIDER UPTAKE context)

Further, the development of the method to assess water smartness and progress towards the SDGs in WIDER UPTAKE has been based on the following points:

- Achieving sustainability implies achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- Sustainability should always be measured in several dimensions, at least social, environmental, and economic.
- Sustainability can be achieved without being water-smart, but a system cannot be water-smart without being sustainable, i.e., water-smart solutions are a subset of sustainable solutions.

The framework is structured under five dimensions: social, environment, economy, governance, and technical performance. Further, a three-level approach with objectives, criteria and indicators has been applied for the assessment.

Stakeholders in the local communities of practice have contributed to the development of the framework through workshops and questionnaires, scoring the relevance of the SDGs and the content of the framework to their demonstration case.

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The results from the questionnaires have been analysed using principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least squares regression (PLSR). The analysis of SDG relevance shows that none of the stakeholder groups scored the relevance of the SDGs clearly different from the other cases, and that SDG 6, 9, 11, 12 and 13 are highly relevant for the solutions being demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE. There were no clear groups based on the demonstration cases in the scoring of the content of the framework either, indicating applicability of the framework for a range of different cases. The results also indicate a consistency throughout the cases in WIDER UPTAKE in the combination of scoring relevance of SDGs and objectives in the framework and show a correlation between the relevance of the objectives in the framework and the most relevant SDGs for the cases.

The framework to be tested in the demonstration cases concludes this report.

1 Introduction

To meet European and global water challenges, a transition to a water-smart society was foreseen in Water Europe's vision document of 2017¹, where a water-smart society was defined as [1]:

"a society in which the true value of water is recognised and realised, and all available water sources are managed in such a way that water scarcity and pollution of groundwater are avoided. Water and resource loops are largely closed to foster a circular economy and optimal resource efficiency, while the water system is resilient against the impact of climate change events"

To achieve the transition to this water-smart society, new, innovative water-smart solutions are needed. Water Europe points to *new digital and water technologies* and *a hybrid grey and green water infrastructure*. The transition is foreseen to boost the economy through the application of circular economy principles, while concepts such as *"Multiple waters"* will contribute to reduce use of freshwater resources by managing several water sources to deliver a water quality fit for the purpose according to different uses in an integrated system. This will also require *inclusive multi-stakeholder governance* where awareness raising, stakeholder views and collaborative decision making are important aspects. Despite the urgent need, the implementation of water-smart solutions is limited due to barriers of technological, organizational, institutional, regulatory, social, and economic character.

The European Union's Horizon 2020 project "Achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions—WIDER UPTAKE" studies a set of innovative symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES) co-developed by water utilities and private businesses from industry sectors with high water consumption, high use of material resources and energy, i.e., agriculture industry, building & manufacturing materials industry, and energy supply.

Five demonstration cases, in a north – south axis including Norway, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Italy and Ghana, cover different governance contexts, socio-economic conditions, availability of water resources, climate and environmental conditions, and TRL scale. The case studies involve five water utilities, six solution providers (five SMEs and one publicly owned company) and ten committed stakeholders representing different industry sectors and authorities. The focus level in WIDER UPTAKE is the symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCESs), which is the term used to describe the types of solutions demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE.

To analyse the different cases and understand how their solutions can achieve wider uptake in different settings, a common methodology for assessing the water smartness of the solutions is required. The development of a framework for such an assessment is the objective of task 5.1, performed in work package 5 (WP5) – Water smartness and sustainability.

¹ In 2023, an updated version of the vision has been published, including a revised definition of a water-smart society. The revision does not change the overall message used as background for the work presented in this report.

2 Objective and structure of the report

The objective of this deliverable is to present the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework, developed within WP5, Task 5.1 – Develop a framework to measure water smartness and progress towards the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The timeline of the task has been from month 1 to 36 in the project period.

This report describes the development and presents the version of the framework to be tested in the demonstration cases. Hence, the results presented here are applied in Task 5.2 – Implement and demonstrate the framework in the demonstration cases, which continues into month 42. The results from Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 will together form the basis for the preparation of a generic version of the water smartness and sustainability framework. This is the content of Task 5.3, to be performed in month 31 to 42. The generic version will be used in the preparation of the roadmap in work package 6 (WP6).

The background presented in the next chapter presents the foundation upon which the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework is built, as the focus of this report is the development process and resulting content of the framework. The communities of practice (CoPs) related to the demonstration cases have been actively involved in giving input and feedback throughout the process, but further details on the specific solutions developed in the demonstration cases and the challenges they address are presented within other parts of the project.

In chapter 4, the input sources and methods applied in the framework development are presented, and the results of the framework development workshops in the local communities of practice (CoPs) and the discussion of these are found in chapter 5. An overview of the content of the framework to be tested in the demonstration cases conclude the report in chapter 6.

Testing of the presented framework has started within Task 5.2, applying a test procedure to be followed by all the demonstration cases. The test procedure and two demonstration cases' take on filling the framework are presented in D5.2, while the testing continues within the timeframe of Task 5.2.

3 Background

Water-smart solutions are needed to meet global water- and resource challenges, as addressed by Water Europe [1,2]. At the same time, the solutions should promote sustainability. So how can such water-smart, sustainable solutions be identified? The objective for the WIDER UPTAKE framework for water smartness and sustainability is to enable a utility, company, water sector planner or decision maker to measure how water-smart a process, a product or solution is, and how it contributes towards achieving the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The framework assessment should also provide a transparent method for ranking alternative processes, products, or solutions with respect to the same.

The point of departure for measuring water smartness in WIDER UPTAKE is the definition of a water-smart society by Water Europe cited in the introduction. This choice was made based on Water Europe's prominent position as *'the voice and promoter of water-related innovation and research- and technological development in Europe'* [3].

Keywords for measuring water smartness were identified in the definition, as indicated in bold text:

*"a society in which the true **value** of water is recognised and realised, and all available water sources are **managed** in such a way that water **scarcity** and **pollution** of groundwater are avoided. Water and resource loops are largely closed to foster a **circular economy and optimal resource efficiency**, while the **water system** is **resilient against the impact of climate change events**" (our addition of bold font)*

Based on these keywords, the following properties related to water smartness have been defined to be covered by the framework:

- Value of and in water
- Water management
- Water scarcity
- Water pollution
- Circularity and resource efficiency
- Resilience
- Symbiotic circular economy solutions (the water system in WIDER UPTAKE context)

More details on WIDER UPTAKE's considerations of each of these properties are presented in MS7 Milestone report – Background for criteria and indicators to assess water smartness and sustainability including contributions from WP2, WP3 and WP4 [4].

A revised version of Water Europe's definition of water-smart society was recently published [2]. The new version is slightly extended with objectives and emphasises the importance of people, both with respect to demographic change and stakeholder engagement. However, the revision does not change the overall message or the identified keywords that has been used as background for the work presented in this deliverable.

Further, the development of the method to assess water smartness and progress towards the SDGs in WIDER UPTAKE has been based on the following points:

- Achieving sustainability implies achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- Sustainability should always be measured in several dimensions, at least social, environmental, and economic.
- Sustainability can be achieved without being water-smart, but a system cannot be water-smart without being sustainable, i.e., water-smart solutions are a subset of sustainable solutions.

The framework developed in WIDER UPTAKE builds upon previous sustainability frameworks for the water sector, e.g., Framework for Sustainability Assessment of UWCS (urban water cycle services) (TRUST project) [5], Framework for evaluating changes in ecosystem services (DESSIN project) [6] and Framework for Integrated Assessment of Water Cycle Services [7]. The choice of sustainability dimensions in WIDER UPTAKE is based on the approach in the previous EU project TRUST (Transitions to the urban water services of tomorrow) [5]. In TRUST, assets and governance were added as required supporting dimensions to the traditional dimensions social, environment and economy for sustainability assessment of urban water cycle services. In WIDER UPTAKE, technical performance is used to describe the assets-dimension, reflecting the assessment being performed on solution level. Hence, the dimensions applied in the WIDER UPTAKE framework are social, environment, economy, governance, and technical performance. Sustainable solutions will lie in the intersection between the regions formed by these five dimensions, as illustrated in Figure 3.1:

Figure 3.1: Assessment dimensions applied in the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

In line with the focus level of the project, the assessment framework in WIDER UPTAKE is targeting information on solution level. Figure 3.2 presents a generic structure of a symbiotic circular economy solution (SCES), which is the term used to describe the types of solutions demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE. The figure also presents how users of the framework should draw the boundaries to define what is within their solution, what should be defined as inputs from society and nature, and what should be defined as impacts (positive or negative) on

society and nature. Figure 3.2 shows the compartments of society and nature providing inputs and receiving impacts, respectively. The inputs and impact will vary for different SCES and should be specified for each specific case both with respect to type and compartment.

For assessment of a specific SCES the properties should be reviewed and those relevant for the given solution should be included in the assessment of water smartness and sustainability.

Figure 3.2: Illustration of properties of a symbiotic circular economy solution (SCES) and the inputs and impacts on its surroundings.

The demonstration cases in the project represent a variety of solutions, addressing different water- and resource challenges:

- Reuse of wastewater for irrigation and production of slow-release fertilizers in agricultural industry, in Sicily, Italy
- Reuse of wastewater for urban agriculture and production of biochar from wastewater sludge for fuel, in Accra, Ghana
- Fertiliser and soil improver by waste and wastewater resource recovery, in Hamar and Stavanger, Norway
- Improved biogas production for the gas grid in Stavanger, Norway
- Reuse of wastewater for greening the urban areas, in Prague, Czech Republic
- Production of new biocomposite material and prototype products from water embedded resources, in Amsterdam, Netherlands

This variety is used to give input to and test the generic applicability of the framework.

4 Framework development

4.1 Input sources

The content of the framework has been built upon existing sustainability assessment frameworks and methods. The solutions' direct contribution to some of the Sustainable Development Goals is included in the framework by incorporation of SDG indicators adapted to solution level. Inspiration for and specific criteria and indicators has also been found in e.g., Ecosystems and Human Well-being [8] Framework for Sustainability Assessment of UWCS (TRUST project) [5], Framework for evaluating changes in ecosystem services (DESSIN project) [6] Framework for Integrated Assessment of Water Cycle Services (SUWAM) [7], Assessing the Value of Resource Recovery and Reuse [9] and Evaluating the Impact of Nature-based Solutions: A Handbook for Practitioners [10], among others. Important input was also received from other work packages in WIDER UPTAKE developing assessment methods on quality-, environmental- and health risk, circularity and resource efficiency, and governance. Indicators applied and developed in these other work packages are used directly in the framework and have been updated as they have developed during the project.

4.2 Framework structure

As presented in previous chapter, the framework is structured under five dimensions: Social, environment, economy, governance, and technical performance. Within each dimension, three objectives have been identified that a symbiotic circular economy solution should achieve in order to be water-smart and contribute to sustainability. These objectives should cover the solution defined by the user of the assessment framework. It is the aim to develop a set of objectives that are generally applicable for all SCESs.

For each objective, a set of criteria has been defined for measuring compliance with the given objective. The criteria should cover the essential properties of the solution needed to assess compliance/achievement of the objective. Quantification of each criterion is done through one or several indicator(s), which should cover a representative selection of solution properties within the given criterion. In addition, the indicators should be SMART, i.e., Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time-bound. To cover a wide range of SCESs, it follows that at least the indicator level in the framework should be possible to adapt in a given assessment. This may also require additional criteria. The aim is therefore to provide a list of standard criteria and indicators, from which a user may select, and supplement by addition of case specific criteria and indicators. To make the framework directly relevant for a given solution, the users will in addition specify some indicators further. E.g., for the indicator "Direct discharge to water of relevant pollutants" the pollutants relevant for the solution to be assessed should be specified.

When developing and implementing symbiotic circular economy solutions, the drinking water- and wastewater utilities may meet new requirements with regards to application of the water and the resources within. This could potentially come in conflict with the requirements for the traditional drinking water and/or wastewater services. To be water-smart and contribute to sustainability, the utilities must balance any conflicting interests and find ways to exploit the

value in water without compromising their role as traditional drinking water- and wastewater service providers. This is dealt with in the framework by differentiated objectives, criteria, and indicators for the traditional services and the SCES, i.e., the new solution.

Another differentiation applied in the framework is between recovered resource(s) and final product(s). This differentiation originates from WP2 in WIDER UPTAKE, from their procedures for monitoring and control of health and quality risks. Typically, the two categories will be a result of two (or more) separate processes, and different regulations apply for each category. The framework reflects this by distinguishing between the two categories in both criteria and indicators, where relevant. In some cases, it is not possible to differentiate between the recovered resource and the product, e.g., in cases with reuse of treated wastewater, water is both the recovered resource in, and the product of the SCES.

4.3 Co-development of the framework with researchers and local stakeholders in WIDER UPTAKE

Two types of workshops were held in the development of the framework. The interdisciplinarity in the team of researchers in WIDER UPTAKE was taken advantage of in online workshops focusing on developing the phrasing of objectives, criteria, and indicators. In addition, workshops in the local communities of practice (CoPs) of each demonstration case were held to connect the SDGs to the solutions and to get feedback on the relevance of the suggested objectives, criteria, and indicators for the given case. The workshops in the local CoPs were typically held together with other work packages to align wanted feedback from the local stakeholders and explore correlations between the work package contents.

In the workshops, online questionnaires were used to map the perception of relevance of each of the SDGs to the cases and to receive feedback on the relevance of the suggested framework content. The questionnaires were set into context by an introduction of the objectives of WP5 and the framework, and an overview of the framework structure. A Likert scale was used for ranging the relevance of each SDG and each objective, criterion, and indicator, where 0 equalled 'not important for my application' and 3 equalled 'very important for my application'. The number of participants and types of stakeholders present in the demonstration cases' workshops varied largely, which is also reflected in the results presented in the next chapters.

To progress towards the framework version to be tested in the demonstration cases, a smaller working group was formed, together representing all the research partners, cases, and countries. The working group discussed the indicators in more detail in view of the different cases. The version to be applied for testing in the demonstration cases was then concluded, and the resulting objectives, criteria and indicators are presented in chapter 6.

4.4 Data analysis

The responses obtained through the questionnaires have been analysed using principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least squares regression (PLSR) [11,12] to assess if the responses are grouped according to the demonstration cases, and if there are correlations in the data. In short, PCA and PLSR score plots show the individual responses in relation to each other and should reveal any grouping. PCA and PLSR loading plots show the relation between the variables, and variables that lie close together in the loading plots are correlated.

PCA and PLSR score plots have been used to analyse if the responses from the stakeholder groups differed between the demonstration cases, and assess the general applicability of the SDGs, objectives, criteria, and indicators for assessing the water smartness and sustainability of the demonstrated solutions.

The PLSR loading plot has been used to analyse correlations between the SDGs and the objectives defined in the developed framework to assess if there were any specific SDGs that were more associated with the objectives in the water smartness and sustainability assessment framework than others.

The input data were the individual responses from 41 stakeholders in the 5 demonstration cases that answered MS Forms questionnaires regarding the relevance of the SDGs, and the WS&S framework objectives, criteria, and indicators for assessing their SCES. The scale used was a Likert scale with levels of 0, 1, 2, or 3, where 0 indicated least relevance and 3 the highest relevance. One of the stakeholders did not submit a response regarding the SDGs and 6 stakeholders did not submit responses regarding the WS&S framework objectives, criteria, and indicators. The input data matrix was therefore a matrix of 41 rows and a total of 148 variables that included the SDGs, WS&S framework objectives, criteria, indicators and 5 variables with text input describing the cases and used to identify sub-sets of the data. For the SDGs one sample contained only missing values. For the WS&S framework objectives, criteria, and indicators, six samples contained only missing values.

The input X matrixes for the PCAs were the subsets of all samples with responses for SDGs, WS&S framework objectives, criteria, and indicators, respectively. The X matrix for the PLSR was the subset of all samples with responses for the WS&S framework objectives, and the Y matrix for the PLSR was the subset of all samples with responses for the SDGs. In the analyses, samples that contained only missing data were excluded.

PCA and PLSR were run using a commercial multivariate analysis software, UnscramblerX v10.4². There was no pre-processing of the input data. The PCAs and PLSR were run without mean centring of the matrixes, full cross validation, and all variables were given equal weight of 1.00.

The score plots shown in the result part of the report are with equal scale on the axes to avoid exaggeration of variation between data points due to scaling of the axis.

² <https://www.aspentech.com/en/products/apm/aspens-unscrambler>

5 Results from framework development workshops

5.1 Relevance of the SDG’s for the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE

In the local communities of practice workshops, the attending stakeholders were asked to rate the relevance of each of the Sustainable Development Goals (Figure 5.1) on a Likert scale from 0, equalling ‘not important for my application’ and 3 equalling ‘very important for my application’. The results from the questionnaires for each of the demonstration cases are presented in Figure 5.2. The type and number of stakeholders varied for the different workshops, which is reflected in the results, but statistical analysis of the responses was not the goal of the questionnaires. The objective of the questionnaires was to get insight into the attending stakeholder’s perception of their case in light of the SDGs.

Figure 5.1: The United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals.

Figure 5.2: The local communities of practice's perception of relevance of the Sustainable Development Goals for the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE, sorted from the most relevant. (0 = Not important for the application, 3 = Very important for the application.)

In the Italian case, the responses are the result of a group work reaching consensus on the score upon submitting, while for the other cases the result to a larger degree reflect the average of several responses. The responses reflect the technologies developed in the different cases, e.g., in Accra, biochar is a final product, mirrored by the high relevance of SDG no. 7, Affordable and clean energy.

The complete data set of individual answers across the cases has been analysed with principal component analysis (PCA) to explore the data for potential grouping. The PCA-scores (Figure 5.3) show some responses that are slightly separate from the majority, but none that are considered outliers in this analysis. Overall, none of the stakeholder groups scored the relevance of the SDGs clearly different from the other cases, which indicates that the overall average (Figure 5.4) is a good representation for all the cases. The mentioned consensus from the group discussion in the Italian case is visible in Figure 5.3 from the two data points for Sicily lying on top of each other.

Figure 5.3: Score plot from principal component analysis of the scores for relevance of the Sustainable Development Goals for the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE.

The sorted average for all cases’ responses for relevance of SDG’s (Figure 5.4) show that the water utilities, with their responsibilities for clean water and sanitation, is at the core of the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE. SDG 6 is followed closely by SDG 9, highlighting the innovative aspects of the demonstrated solutions, as SDG 9 is to build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation. The new solutions are also seen as highly relevant in taking action to combat climate change and its impacts (SDG 13), make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable (SDG 11) and ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns (SDG12).

Figure 5.4: Average responses on relevance of the Sustainable Development Goals for the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE. (0 = Not important for the application, 3 = Very important for the application.)

5.2 Feedback from researchers and local CoPs on initial suggested framework content

Questionnaires were also used to receive feedback on the content of the initial versions of the framework. The attendees in the previous mentioned workshops in the local CoPs were asked to rate each objective, criteria, and indicator on a Likert scale from 0, equalling ‘not important for my application’ to 3, equalling ‘very important for my application’.

The data set of individual answers across the demonstration cases were also for this questionnaire analysed by PCA. Figure 5.5 – Figure 5.7 show the PCA score plot for the objectives, criteria, and indicators, respectively. The analyses for the objectives and criteria show no clear grouping of the demonstration cases, except for the Italian case in the score plot for the objectives (Figure 5.5). In the analysis of the indicators, the scores for the Dutch case lie below the main cluster except for one data point. The result for the Italian case can again be explained by the mentioned group work, resulting in only two answers aligned with each other. The Dutch demonstration case is somewhat different from the other cases because the main focus is on biocomposite materials rather than wastewater reuse, and resource recovery from sludge for fertilisers or energy as in the other demonstration cases. Another difference is in the

respondent group, which for the Dutch case were private industry representatives and researchers, while utilities were not represented. This may have influenced the scores.

Figure 5.5: Score plot from principal component analysis of the scores for relevance of the objectives in the water smartness and sustainability framework for the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE.

Figure 5.6: Score plot from principal component analysis of the scores for relevance of the criteria in the water smartness and sustainability framework for the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE.

Figure 5.7: Score plot from principal component analysis of the scores for relevance of the indicators in the water smartness and sustainability framework for the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE.

Figure 5.8 shows the overall score for the categories Objectives, Criteria and Indicators based on the responses from the workshops. Once again, 0 equals ‘Not important for the application’, while 3 equals ‘Very important for the application’. One workshop was held online for the researcher team in WIDER UPTAKE, while the other responses come from the local CoP workshops.

Figure 5.8: Responses from the researcher team and the local communities of practice on relevance for the categories Objectives, Criteria and Indicators in the initial version of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework. (0 = Not important for the application, 3 = Very important for the application.)

The researchers gave a high overall score for both the objectives, criteria, and indicators, whereas larger differences can be seen between the three levels from the demonstration cases’

point of view. This can be explained as a reflection of the local differences in the cases; The framework aims to cover a wide variety of solutions with the possibility of local adaption, leading to differences in relevance of certain criteria and indicators. The high overall score for objectives shows that the researchers and stakeholders attending the workshops finds the set of objectives suitable to assess the solutions demonstrated in the project.

The individual scores for each objective, criterion, and indicator from each workshop (plots not included in this report) were also analysed to identify low scores to consider removal or rephrasing. Most of the low scores from a given case could be found on criteria and indicator level and could be explained by the properties of the solution in question, but also related to the type of stakeholders present in the workshop. The focus of a given stakeholder can be concentrated around a certain dimension or certain parts of the framework, which again could be connected to the maturity of the solution.

The scores given by the stakeholders in the cases through these questionnaires were considered in the refinement of the framework done by the working group and in concluding the version to be tested in the demonstration cases. This testing version of the framework is presented in the next chapter.

5.3 Relation between SDGs and the objectives of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

Partial Least Square Regression has been used to explore the relation between the responses from the communities of practise on relevance for the cases for the SDGs and for the objectives in the water smartness and sustainability framework. In the analysis, the scores of relevance for the objectives in the water smartness and sustainability framework were the X-matrix and the scores for relevance of the SDGs were the Y-matrix.

There are no clear groupings in the PLSR score plot in Figure 5.9, which indicates that there is consistency throughout the cases in WIDER UPTAKE in the combination of scoring relevance of SDGs and objectives in the framework. Again, the Italian case stands out because of the two answers resulting from a group work.

The PLSR loading plot in Figure 5.10 shows three groups of SDG loadings, which are related to the responses of relevance for the cases. The group in the upper left corner represents the SDGs with an average relevance lower than 1, i.e., less relevant for the applications (SDG 1, 4, 5, 10 and 16). The group in the middle are the SDGs with an average relevance between 1 and 2 (SDG 2, 3, 7, 8, 14, 15 and 17). The SDGs with the highest relevance for the applications, i.e., SDG 6, 9, 11, 12 and 13, can be found among the loadings for the objectives in the framework. This shows a correlation between the relevance of the objectives in the framework and the most relevant SDGs for the cases, which indicates that the respondents represented in this data set find the objectives relevant in connection to these SDGs. This correlation will be investigated further in the testing of the framework.

Figure 5.9: Score plot from principal least squares regression with the scores for relevance of the objectives in the water smartness and sustainability framework as X and the scores for relevance of the SDGs in the water smartness and sustainability framework as Y.

Figure 5.10: Loading plot from principal least squares regression with the scores for relevance of the objectives in the water smartness and sustainability framework as X and the scores for relevance of the SDGs in the water smartness and sustainability framework as Y.

6 Framework version for testing

In the following tables, the framework version to be applied in testing in the demonstration cases is presented, which concludes this report. The testing itself is the subject of deliverable D5.2. First, the objectives within each dimension are presented in Table 6.1. Next, the criteria identified to measure compliance with each of the objectives are listed by dimension in Table 6.2 to Table 6.6. The indicators, with their units, for each dimension are given in Table 6.7 to Table 6.11.

Table 6.1: Objectives for the five assessment dimensions in the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

Dimension	No.	Objective
Sosial (S)	S1	Maintain the social benefits provided by traditional water-and/or wastewater utilities
	S2	Provide human well-being by the recovered resources and final products of the SCES
	S3	Enhance knowledge and acceptance of the SCES, its recovered resources and final products
Environment (En)	En1	Minimize negative environmental impacts
	En2	Preserve nature
	En3	Have positive climate effect
Economic (Ec)	Ec1	Maximise the economic value added in/by/through the SCES value chain
	Ec2	Give added economic benefits to the parties of the SCES
	Ec3	Give added economic benefits to society
Governance (G)	G1	Comply with regulations, rules, and guidelines
	G2	Contribute towards Integrated Water Management
	G3	Have participatory governance
Technical Performance (TP)	TP1	Achieve targets for traditional services provided by water-and/or wastewater utilities
	TP2	Deliver correct quality and quantity of the recovered resources and final products of the SCES
	TP3	Minimize waste and keep resources in use

Table 6.2: Criteria for the objectives in the social dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Objective	No.	Criterion
S1	Maintain the social benefits provided by traditional water- and/or wastewater utilities	S1.1	Provision of universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water
		S1.2	Provision of access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene
		S1.3	Equity in the allocation of water and resources in water across social and economic groups
S2	Provide human well-being by the recovered resources and final products of the SCES	S2.1	Secure resource access
		S2.2	Access to goods
		S2.3	Positive and/or negative impacts on human health
		S2.4	Values and norms
S3	Enhance knowledge and acceptance of the SCES, its recovered resources and final products	S3.1	Citizen involvement in education activities related to the SCES
		S3.2	Amount of information available related to the SCES

Table 6.3: Criteria for the objectives in the environment dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Objective	No.	Criterion
En1	Minimize negative environmental impacts	En1.1	Net environmental impacts from the processes to provide water services, recover resources and produce final products
		En1.2	Direct and indirect discharges assessed by criteria from regulations for water, soil, and air for different types of pollution specified further in indicators
		En1.3	Risk of environmental impact from the application of final products
		En1.4	Contribution to counteract physical shortage of water (of sufficient quality)
En2	Preserve nature	En2.1	Effect on biodiversity
En3	Have positive climate effect	En3.1	Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions
		En3.2	Reduction of atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations
		En3.3	Micro climate regulation

Table 6.4: Criteria for the objectives in the economy dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Objective	No.	Criterion
Ec1	Maximise the economic value added in/by/through the SCES value chain	Ec1.1	Value added for the involved actors
Ec2	Give added economic benefits to the parties of the SCES	Ec2.1	Business growth
Ec3	Give added economic benefits to society	Ec3.1	Socioeconomic values enabled by the SCES
		Ec3.2	Affordability of services and products for end users

Table 6.5: Criteria for the objectives in the governance dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Objective	No.	Criterion
G1	Comply with regulations, rules, and guidelines	G1.1	Requirements given by design criteria/rules/guidelines
		G1.2	Existing legislative and regulatory requirements
G2	Contribute towards Integrated Water Management	G2.1	Assurance of sufficient quantity of water of required quality within the water sector
		G2.2	Assurance of sufficient quantity of water of required quality for other sectors of society, e.g., agriculture
		G2.3	Assurance of sufficient quantity of water of required quality for nature
		G2.4	Assurance of sufficient quantity of recovered resources of required quality
		G2.5	Alignment with policies for other sectors, e.g., agriculture, aquaculture, energy
G3	Have participatory governance	G3.1	Transparency
		G3.2	Involvement in water management

Table 6.6: Criteria for the objectives in the technical performance dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Objective	No.	Criterion
TP1	Achieve targets for traditional services provided by water- and/or wastewater utilities	TP1.1	Satisfactory treatment of water for municipal or industrial supply and/or wastewater for discharge
		TP1.2	Satisfactory quantity of water for municipal or industrial supply
		TP1.3	Satisfactory treatment of residuals from treatment of water for supply and/or wastewater for discharge
		TP1.4	Reliability of water infrastructure
		TP1.5	Resilience against the impact of climate change events
TP2	Deliver correct quality and quantity of the recovered resources and final products of the SCES	TP2.1	Quality and quantity of recovered resources in the SCES
		TP2.2	Quality and quantity of final products from the SCES
TP3	Minimize waste and keep resources in use	TP3.1	Material circularity

Table 6.7: Indicators in the social dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Indicator	Unit
S1.1.1	Proportion of population or number of people provided with drinking water services from the SCES	% or person equivalents
S1.2.2	Proportion or number of person equivalents of household wastewater flow safely treated by the SCES	% or person equivalents
S1.2.2	Proportion or person equivalents of industrial wastewater flow safely treated by the SCES	% or person equivalents
S1.3.1	Percent of population with access to the services provided by the SCES	%
S2.1.1	Fraction total resource need covered by recovered resources from the SCES	%
S2.2.1	Fraction total need covered by final products from the SCES	%
S2.3.1	Microbial risk (QMRA as proposed by WP2, or other methods)	DALYs pppy
S2.3.2	Chemical risk (QCRA as proposed by WP2, or other methods) measured as RCR= (estimated daily intake dose)/TDI	Ratio (0-1)
S2.4.1	Perceived positive feeling of using products from recycled resources	Likert scale (1-5)
S2.4.2	Bequest value - measured by willingness to pay to ensure that peoples' offspring or future generations inherit a particular environmental asset	€ or other currency per unit of recovered resource or final product
S3.1.1	No. of people involved in educational activities	Number
S3.2.1	No. of citations; information linked to recovered waste(s) and final product(s); number of communications	Number

Table 6.8: Indicators in the environment dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Indicator	Unit
En1.1.1	Indicators from LCA	Net impacts of different categories per functional unit
En1.2.1	Direct discharge to water of relevant pollutants, e.g., ammonia	Mass of pollutant per time period, e.g., kg NH ₄ -N/year
En1.2.2	Direct discharge to soil of relevant pollutants, e.g., cadmium	Mass of pollutant per time period, e.g., kg Cd/year
En1.2.3	Direct discharge to air of relevant pollutants, e.g., nitrous oxide	Mass of pollutant per time period, e.g., kg N ₂ O/year
En1.2.4	Indirect discharge to water of relevant pollutants, e.g., ammonia	Mass of pollutant per time period, e.g., kg NH ₄ -N/year
En1.2.5	Indirect discharge to soil of relevant pollutants, e.g., cadmium	Mass of pollutant per time period, e.g., kg Cd/year
En1.2.6	Indirect discharge to air of relevant pollutants, e.g., nitrous oxide	Mass of pollutant per time period, e.g., kg N ₂ O/year
En1.3.1	Chemical risk for water RCR=PEC/PNEC	Ratio (0-1)
En1.3.2	Chemical risk for soil RCR=PEC/PNEC	Ratio (0-1)
En1.3.3	Chemical risk for air RCR=PEC/PNEC	Ratio (0-1)
En1.4.1	Relevant (green, blue, or grey) water footprint of the SCES	Water volume per functional unit, e.g., litres per kg final product
En2.1.1	Number of species or type of species negatively affected	Number
En2.1.2	Number of environmental compartments negatively affected	Number
En2.1.2	Number of environmental compartments negatively affected	Number
En3.1.1	CO ₂ footprint per unit volume of water managed	kg CO ₂ eq/m ³
En3.2.1	CO ₂ uptake per unit volume of water managed	ppm CO ₂ eq/m ³
En3.3.1	Reduced heat island effect	Number of days/year

Table 6.9: Indicators in the economy dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Indicator	Unit
Ec1.1.1	Value of recovered resources per functional unit	€/functional unit
Ec1.1.2	Value of final products per functional unit	€/functional unit
Ec2.1.1	Growth in annual income	%
Ec2.1.2	Annual growth in number of clients/customers	%
Ec2.1.3	Increase in number of products/services compared with before the SCES	%
Ec2.1.4	Increase in number of value chains	%
Ec3.1.1	Increase in jobs in the water sector	%
Ec3.1.2	Water use efficiency (UN)	€/m ³ water used
Ec3.2.1	Price change for costumers	%
Ec3.2.2	Investment cost	€/functional unit
Ec3.2.3	Operational cost	€/functional unit/year

Table 6.10: Indicators in the governance dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Indicator	Unit
G1.1.1	Degree of compliance with design criteria/rules/guidelines, e.g., regarding environment; climate change adaptation; materials/construction; performance/ functionality	Likert scale (1-5)
G1.2.1	Degree of compliance with existing legislative and regulatory requirements for the recovered resources	Likert scale (1-5)
G1.2.2	Degree of compliance with existing legislative and regulatory requirements for the final products	Likert scale (1-5)
G2.1.1	Degree of compliance with existing regulations and guidelines in the water sector for quantity and quality of water for different uses	Likert scale (1-5)
G2.2.1	Degree of compliance with existing regulations for quantity and quality related to use of water in other sectors of society	Likert scale (1-5)
G2.3.1	Degree of compliance with existing regulations and guidelines for quantity and quality of water related to environmental flow requirements	Likert scale (1-5)
G2.4.1	Degree of compliance with existing regulations and guidelines for quantity of recovered resources of required quality in different sectors of society	Likert scale (1-5)
G2.5.1	Degree of alignment with existing regulations in other sectors, e.g., agriculture, aquaculture, energy	Likert scale (1-5)
G3.1.1	Openness of participatory processes	Likert scale (1-5)
G3.2.1	Interactions with stakeholders	Number of stakeholder categories involved in the SCES

Table 6.11: Indicators in the technical performance dimension of the WIDER UPTAKE water smartness and sustainability framework.

No.	Indicator	Unit
TP1.1.1	Frequency of not achieving the water quality standards for different applications	#/year
TP1.2.1	Hydraulic reliability of water supply for different applications	Ratio (0-1)
TP1.3.1	Frequency of not achieving the quality standards for residuals, which may have different applications	#/year
TP1.4.1	Frequency of undesirable incidents per year	#/year
TP1.4.2	Frequency of required maintenance	#/year
TP1.5.1	Drop in achievement of primary function targets with flooding or draught of a specified severity, e.g., return period for a flood event	%
TP1.5.2	Duration of not achieving primary function targets after end of flooding or draught	days
TP2.1.1	Frequency of the recovered resources not fulfilling the regulatory requirement or relevant guidelines for quality	#/year
TP2.1.2	Frequency of the recovered resources not fulfilling the required quantity	#/year
TP2.2.1	Frequency of the final products not fulfilling the regulatory requirement or relevant guidelines for quality	#/year
TP2.2.2	Frequency of the final products not fulfilling the required quantity	#/year
TP3.1.1	Material Circularity Indicator for relevant components	Ratio (0-1)

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